

A conjecture about a particular type of polynomials

Conjecture. There are infinite polynomials of the form $n^2 + n + x$, where $n, x \in \mathbb{N}$ that generate infinite prime numbers.

Note: A famous polynomial is the Euler polynomial, which has the form $n^2 + n + 41$, that generates only prime numbers for $n=0, \dots, 39$. But, for $n=40$ we have $40^2 + 40 + 41 = 1681$, that is not a prime number. In fact, 1681 is divisible by 1, 41, 1681.